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Financial Management for Non-Government Organization

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Abstract

The every organization need money or funds. Alongside staff, money is the one thing that takes up most management time. NGO Required Financial Management for the running of different activities for implementation Project for community development and organized awareness program for rural and urban areas. . Good financial management involves Keeping Record, Internal control, Budgeting, Financial reporting .That reasons NGOs need to require to proper controlling and handling for their fund. The funding that caused severe financial difficulties for many non-profit organisations (NGOs). This study examined whether or not NGOs employed sound financial management practices and whether the use of financial management practices has affected non-profit organisations.

Keyword: Finance, Management, Scope, Importance, NGOs.

Introduction

Financial management is crucial for the success of any organization, be it private, government or non-government. Successful enterprises watch their finances very closely and therefore take the right decisions at the right time, ultimately leading to success. Most businesses have a well structured finance department responsible for looking after the accounts and finances of the company. On the other hand, NGOs most often do not consider financial management to be a priority and lack adequate financial knowledge. This is often characterized by poor financial planning and adequate financial systems in place. Very often NGOs work effortlessly towards implementing projects that cater to the need of deprived people and in this process do not pay enough attention to financial control. This practice makes the NGOs vulnerable to financial losses. In the absence of proper backup plans and funds, NGOs are unable to cope with funding crisis. NGOs should realize that managing their finances is of critical importance and they should

incorporate necessary measures towards risk management, resource mobilization and budgeting. It is the responsibility of NGO leaders to plan their expenditures and investments and manage funds in a way that leads to a sustainable enterprise. The purpose of this guide is to introduce NGOs to basic financial procedures and systems that are required for efficient functioning of an NGO. By implementing the procedures and systems mentioned in the guide you will be able to manage your finances and accounts more competently.

This brief introduction outlines how to take proper care of your funds. Good financial management involves the following four building blocks:

1. Keeping Records: The foundations of all accounting are basic records that describe your earnings and spending. This means the contracts and letters for money you receive and the receipts and the invoices for things that you buy. These basic records prove that each and every transaction has taken place. They are the cornerstones of being accountable. You must make sure that all these records are carefully filed and kept safe. You must also make sure that you write down the details of each transaction. Write them down in a 'cashbook' - which is a list of how much you spent, on what and when. If you are keeping your basic records in good order and writing down the details of each transaction in a cashbook then you cannot go far wrong.

2. Internal Control: Make sure that your organisation has proper controls in place so that money cannot be misused. Controls always have to be adapted to different organisations. However, some controls that are often used include:

- Keeping cash in a safe place (ideally in a bank account).
- Making sure that all expenditure is properly authorised.
- Following the budget.
- Monitoring how much money has been spent on what every month.
- Employing qualified finance staff.
- Having an audit every year.

Carrying out a 'bank reconciliation' every month - which means checking that the amount of cash you have in the bank is the same as the amount that your cashbook tells you that you ought to have. This last control is particularly important. It proves that the amounts recorded in the cashbook and the reports based on it are accurate.

3. Budgeting: For good financial management, you need to prepare accurate budgets, in order to know how much money you will need to carry out your work. A budget is only useful if it is worked out by carefully forecasting how much you expect to spend on your activities. The first

step in preparing a good budget is to identify exactly what you hope to do and how you will do it. List your activities, then plan how much they will cost and how much income they will generate.

4. Financial Reporting: The fourth building block is writing and reviewing financial reports. A financial report summarises your income and expenditure over a certain period of time. Financial reports are created by adding together similar transactions. For instance, this might mean adding together all the money you spent on fuel, new tyres and vehicle insurance and calling them "Transport Costs". Financial reports summarise the information held in the cashbook. This is normally done using a system of codes, to allocate transactions to different categories. These categories might often be defined by donors.

The Scope of Financial Management for NGOs

Financial management is generally divided into three broad categories, namely capital structure, capital budgeting and short-term financial management (also referred to as working capital management). An NPO, however, typically does not generate its own income and relies on external sources for its funding, making debt, with its commitment to monthly interest repayments, extremely risky and hence undesirable (C. Masters, CEO of C Masters Development Services (CMDS), personal communication, 10 June 2010). In addition, an NPO does not have shareholders and hence its capital structure does not include a substantial equity component and so the relevance of capital structure theory for NPOs is limited. Unlike capital structure, capital budgeting can "... have a dramatic impact on the character of an NPO for many years since they often involve the commitment of extensive resources over a long period of time" (Gaertner, 1982: 46). This paper, however, seeks to examine the impact of the global financial recession on NPOs' financial viability, which is a function of their ability to meet short-term financial commitments. As a result this study focuses specifically on short-term financial management.

Short-Term Financial Management for NGOs: inflows and outflows occurring within the next twelve months, and comprises cash management, inventory management and accounts receivable management. For most NPOs the issues of inventory management and accounts receivable management are likely to be less significant but the forecasting/budgeting of future cash requirements and management of cash is critical.

Budgeting and Forecasting : Budgeting is seen as one of the most challenging areas of managing an organisation's finances (Hankin, Seidner and Zietlow, 1997: 147). One of the chief advantages of budgeting for an NPO is that if planned and executed properly, the likelihood of the NPO being economically sustainable is improved (Blazek, 2008: 71). In the 1970s, it was common practice to advocate zero-base budgeting (ZBB), which requires managers to justify their entire

budgets each year with no base level of spending being assumed, but it was found to be extremely time consuming and is seldom used (Anthony and Young, 1999: 453). The incremental approach treats existing programmes as preapproved, subject only to changes in financial resources allocated, which means that it is less time consuming and is also felt to be less threatening to managers of programmes (Blazek, 2008: 69). Gambino and Reardon (1981 cited in Zietlow, 1989: 220) note that with regards to the well-established NPOs in their study, the use of budgeting and forecasting in particular was generally poor.

Management of Cash Resources: Often, the most important resource for a NPO is its cash (Blazek, 2008: 107). Zietlow and Seidner (2007: 13) suggest that the primary objective of NPOs should be striving to meet an “approximate liquidity target” over time. By doing so, a sound cash flow management system can assist an organisation to survive any periods of strain or uncertainty. Cash management is, thus, often used as an important indicator of the “fundamental health” of an NPO, with Pajas and Vilain (2004: 352) suggesting that, because NPOs usually do not worry about maximising their profits but do need cash to operate, cash management is even more important for the nonprofit sector.

Performance Analysis: Accountability is seen as the number one priority for NPOs, both to the people or cause it may support and to donors/funders who commit financial resources to the NPO. However, performance analysis is an area in which NPOs are particularly weak (Evans, 2010: 26, 27). Performance measurement can be multi-faceted, with two of the common techniques for NPOs being ratio analysis and variance analysis.

Ratio Analysis : Various ratios are used for both internal and external monitoring as “measurement of financial performance by ratio analysis helps identify organisational strengths and weaknesses by detecting financial anomalies and focusing attention on issues of organisational importance (Glynn et al. 2003, cited in Abraham, 2006: 1). Ratio analysis can thus be used as a control mechanism for long-run targeting (Zietlow, 1989: 226). Zietlow and Seidner (2007: 4), however, observe that the majority of NPOs do not use ratio analysis, a statement borne out by Zietlow’s (1989: 225) finding that only 17% of his respondents employed ratio analysis.

Importance of Financial Management for NGOs

As a NGO you might be thinking your primary task is to work towards social service and not financial management. But unless your finances and funds are sorted, you cannot achieve your objectives. The primary significance of financial planning and management in NGOs lies in achieving its overall goals and objectives. Here are some points indicating the importance of financial management for an NGO.

1. Being accountable to the donors: Most NGOs rely completely on funding and therefore having proper accounting systems in place becomes all the more important. As a NGO you need to be accountable to the donor agencies and individuals who support your cause. With proper systems in place you can keep track of your expenditures and submit timely reports to them. This would lead to enhanced trust between you and the donor, thereby increasing the chances of your NGO getting a continuous support from them. With limited funding it is important for an NGO to manage all the funds in a careful manner. Furthermore, proper finance systems will also help the NGO maintain financial reports and showcase their entire spending to the regulatory bodies as per the agreed terms.
2. Securing future: The present financial condition of any organization determines its future. In a similar manner, NGOs should also opt for sustainable use of finance. This simply means that NGOs should spend in their present ventures, keeping in mind the future. After all, it is quite important to have future plans and become well secured as well as future-ready.
3. Eliminating fraud and theft: Malpractices and illegal deeds such as overuse of resources, fraud and theft have become prevalent among NGOs. Firm checks are mandatory, for minimizing such illicitness and preventing abuse of resources. With complete financial planning, coordination and control, these issues can be easily addressed.
4. Making productive decisions: With sound financial management, NGOs can make more productive decisions concerning resource allocation, fund raising, fund mobilizing and other undertakings. Good decision making skill enables right amount of funds to be invested at the right place. Funds are therefore efficiently and optimally utilized.
5. Achieving objectives: Every NGO is guided by certain policies and procedures, which are related to its overall objectives. Each decision that is undertaken by the authority is driven towards successful achievement of its set goals and objectives. Without organizing finance, it will be difficult for the organization and its employees to reach its aim and fulfill purpose of its existence.
6. Enhancing credibility: Managing finance is a matter of skills and tactics that ideally changes from time to time. With excellent finance management, NGOs enhance their image that enhances its value and making them more credible. By framing well defined financial plans and policies NGOs also earn good reputation within its community. They

can also improve their current position and look forward to gain trust, faith and reliability.

7. Strengthening fundraising efforts: Most of the NGOs solely survive on its funds. Well organized financial resources help in strengthening fundraising efforts by giving an overall idea about available finance and the amount of finance that needs to be accumulated. Thus, employees get a fair idea regarding the expected amount and plan their fundraising ventures accordingly.

Conclusions

The primary finding of the study was that the majority of NGOs surveyed employed accepted financial management practices and that no relationship between their overall use and an NGO's financial vulnerability was evident. NGOs play a major role in addressing a variety of social challenges and yet relatively little research has been done regarding their financial management and sustainability. A greater theoretical and empirical understanding of NGOs' financial management offers the promise of improving their effectiveness. The Financial Management is very importance to NGOs for their good future and increasing their vision, mission and achieving goal with the help of their own activity to providing benefits for society, community and their staff and voluntaries. As well as maintain his record in time for government audit and clarity of finical statement of Organisation.

References

- Jacobs, Alex. Financial Management for NGOs. n.d. <http://www.gdrc.org/ngo/financial-mgmt.html>.
- Abraham, A. (2006). 'Financial Management in the Nonprofit Sector: A Mission-Based Approach to Ratio Analysis in Membership Organization.' *The Journal of American Academy of Business*. 9(2); 212-217.
- Anthony, R. N., and Young, D. W. (1999). *Management Control in Nonprofit Organizations*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Bird, P. (1985). 'The Level of Reserves in Fund-Raising Charities'. *Financial Accountability & Management*. 1(2); 161-171.
- Blazek, J. (2008). *Nonprofit Financial Planning Made Easy*. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons.
- Copeland, T. E., and Smith, K. V. (1978). 'An Overview of Nonprofit Organizations'. *Journal of Economics and Business*. 30; 21 – 27.

- Department of Social Development. 2005. Assessment of NPO Act. Pretoria: Government Printer.
- Department of Social development Annual Report. (2009). [Online] Available: <http://www.info.gov.za/view/>
- DownloadFileAction?id=108498 (Accessed 18 February 2010).
- Evans, M.H. (2010). Excellence in Financial Management. Course 15: Creating Value in the Nonprofit Sector. [Online] Available:
- <http://www.exinfm.com/training/> [Accessed: 07 July 2010].
- Hankin, J.A., Seidner, A., Zietlow, J. (1997) Financial Management for Nonprofit Organizations. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Krug, K. and Weinberg, C.B. (2004). ‘Mission, Money, and Merit: Strategic Decision Making by Nonprofit Managers’. Nonprofit
- Management & Leadership. 14(3); 325-342.
- LeRoux, K.M. (2005). “What Drives Nonprofit Entrepreneurship? A look at budget trends of Metro Detroit Social Services Agencies”.
- American Review of Public Administration. 35(4); 350-362.
- Pajas, P., and Vilain, M. (2004). Finance of Nonprofit Organizations. In Zimmer, A. and Priller, E. Future of Civil Society: Making Central
- European Nonprofit Organizations Work. Weisbaden, Germany: V.S. Verlag fur Sozialwissenschaften.
- York, P. (2009). The Sustainability Formula: How Nonprofit Organizations Can Thrive in the Emerging Economy. New York: TCC Group.
- Zietlow, J. T. (1989) ‘Capital and Operating Budgeting Practices in Pure Nonprofit Organizations’. Financial Accountability and
- Management. 5(4): 219 – 232.
- Zietlow, J. T., and Seidner, A. G. (2007). Cash & Investment Management for Nonprofit Organizations. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- www.google.co.in